

UNIFOOD CONFERENCE

University of Belgrade

Book of Abstracts

Belgrade, September 24-25, 2021

CIP - Kategorizacija u publikaciji Narodna biblioteka Srbije, Beograd

CIP - Каталогизација у публикацији - Народна библиотека Србије, Београд

663/664(048)

UNIFOOD conference (2021 ; Beograd)

Program i zbornik radova = Book of Abstracts / Unifood conference, Belgrade, September 24-25, 2021 ;
[editors Mirjana Pešić, Živoslav Tešić].

- Belgrade : University of Belgrade, 2021 (Beograd : Razvojno-istraživački centar Grafičkog inženjerstva TMF).
- 197 str. ; 30 cm

Tiraž 30.

ISBN 978-86-7522-066-4

a) Храна - Апстракти

COBISS.SR-ID 47517705

UNIFOOD Conference, Belgrade September 24-25 2021

Book of Abstracts

Published by

University of Belgrade
Studentski trg 1
11000 Belgrade
www.bg.ac.rs,
email: kabinet@rect.bg.ac.rs

For Publisher

Ivanka Popović, rector

Editors

Mirjana Pešić
Živoslav Tešić

Cover Design Layout

Ivana Isaković

Circulation

30

ISBN 978-86-7522-066-4

Print

Razvojno-istraživački centar Grafičkog inženjerstva
Faculty of Technology and Metallurgy, Karnegijeva 4, Belgrade

Published

2021.

UNIFood2021 Conference

24th-25th September 2021 University of Belgrade

2nd International UNIFood Conference

SCIENTIFIC COMMITTEE

Prof. Dr Mirjana Pešić - University of Belgrade, Faculty of Agriculture, Serbia – President of Scientific Committee

Members:

Prof. Dr Ivanka Popović, University of Belgrade, Faculty of Technology and Metallurgy, Rector
Prof. Dr Petar Marin - University of Belgrade, Faculty of Biology, Vice-rector
Prof. Dr Viktor Nedović - University of Belgrade, Faculty of Agriculture
Dr Marina Soković - University of Belgrade, Institute for Biological Research "Siniša Stanković"
Prof. Dr Živoslav Tešić - University of Belgrade, Faculty of Chemistry
Prof. Dr Bojana Vidović - University of Belgrade, Faculty of Pharmacy
Prof. Dr Jelena Lozo - University of Belgrade, Faculty of Biology
Prof. Dr Ljiljana Gojković-Bukarica - University of Belgrade, School of Medicine
Prof. Dr Dušanka Milojković-Opsenica - University of Belgrade, Faculty of Chemistry
Prof. Dr Branko Bugarski - University of Belgrade, Faculty of Technology and Metallurgy
Prof. Dr Jevrosima Stevanović - University of Belgrade, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine
Prof. Dr Milica Fotirić-Akšić - University of Belgrade, Faculty of Agriculture
Prof. Dr Slađana Stanojević, University of Belgrade, Faculty of Agriculture
Prof. Dr Aleksandar Kostić - University of Belgrade, Faculty of Agriculture
Doc Dr Steva Lević - University of Belgrade, Faculty of Agriculture
Prof. dr Nikola Tomić - University of Belgrade, Faculty of Agriculture
Dr Dragana Stanić-Vučinić - University of Belgrade, Faculty of Chemistry
Dr Jelena Begović - Institute of Molecular Genetics and Genetic Engineering
Dr Nataša Golić - University of Belgrade, Institute of Molecular Genetics and Genetic Engineering
Dr Vuk Maksimović - University of Belgrade, Institute for Multidisciplinary Research
Dr Nevena Mihailović-Stanojević - University of Belgrade, Institute for Medical Research
Dr Uroš Gašić - University of Belgrade, Institute for Biological Research "Siniša Stanković"
Dr Tomislav Tosti - University of Belgrade, Faculty of Chemistry
Dr Bojana Balanč - University of Belgrade, Faculty of Technology and Metallurgy
Prof. Dr Je Yang - Shanghai Institute of Materia Medica, Chinese Academy of Sciences (SIMM), China
Prof. Dr Farid Chemat - Université d'Avignon et des Pays du Vaucluse, Avignon, France
Prof. Dr Jose Maria Lagaron - Institute of Agrochemistry and Food Technology (IATA) of the Spanish Council for Scientific Research (CSIC) , Valencia, Spain
Prof. Dr Charalampos Proestos, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens Zografou, Athens, Greece
Dr Didier Dupont, French National Institute for Agriculture Research, France
Dr Linda Giblin, Teagasc Food Research Centre, Moorepark, Ireland
Prof Dr Marco Arlorio, Associate Professor of Food Chemistry at the Dipartimento di Scienze del Farmaco, Università del Piemonte Orientale, Novara, Italy
Prof. Dr Isabela Ferreira - Polytechnic Institute of Braganca, Coordinator of the Mountain Research Centre (CIMO), Portugal
Dr Irena Vovk –National Institute of Chemistry, Ljubljana, Slovenia
Prof. Dr Gertrud Morlock - Justus Liebig University Giessen, Germany
Sokol Abazi, Canadian institute of technology, Tirana and Noval Laboratory Durres, Albania
Prof. Dr Verica Dragović-Uzelac – Faculty of Food Technology and Biotechnology, Zagreb, Croatia
Nikolaos Tzortzakis, Cyprus University of Technology, Department of Agricultural Sciences, Biotechnology and Food Science, Limassol, Cyprus
Prof. Dr Dražen Lušić, Department of Environmental Health Faculty of Medicine, University of Rijeka Croatia
Dr Dorisa Čela, Noval Laboratory, Durres, Albania

UNIFood2021 Conference

24th-25th September 2021 University of Belgrade

2nd International UNIFood Conference

ORGANIZING COMMITTEE

Ivana Isaković - University of Belgrade, Serbia

Nevena Arandjelović - University of Belgrade, Serbia

Nikola Savić - University of Belgrade, Serbia

Dr Ana Salević - University of Belgrade, Faculty of Agriculture, Serbia

MSc Petar Batinić, Institute for Medicinal Plant Research „Dr Josif Pančić“, Belgrade, Serbia

MSc Danijel Milinčić – University of Belgrade, Faculty of Agriculture, Serbia

MSc Dušan Radojević, University of Belgrade, Institute of Molecular Genetics and Genetic Engineering, Serbia

MSc Marina Kostić - University of Belgrade, Institute for Biological Research "Siniša Stanković"

PROBIOTIC IMPACT ON GLICLAZIDE PERMEABILITY

Maja Danić¹, Nebojša Pavlović², Bojan Stanimirov³, Slavica Lazarević¹, Saša Vukmirović¹, Momir Mikov¹

¹*Department of Pharmacology, Toxicology and Clinical Pharmacology, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Serbia*

²*Department of Pharmacy, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Serbia*

³*Department of Biochemistry, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Serbia*

**Corresponding author: maja.djanic@mf.uns.ac.rs*

Interindividual differences in drug response sometimes occur due to the impact of the intestinal environment on drugs, mainly due to the effects of gut microflora. Given that gliclazide is a drug with wide interindividual variation in oral bioavailability, this study aimed to determine the effects of probiotic bacteria on its permeability. The permeability of gliclazide with and without probiotic bacteria was tested using in vitro PAMPA model at pH 7.4 for 6h. In order to study the potential accumulation of gliclazide in probiotic bacteria or biotransformation, the total mass was calculated as a sum of mass in the acceptor and donor compartment. Concentrations of gliclazide were determined by HPLC analysis at 229 m. Probiotic bacteria significantly increased the permeability of gliclazide across the PAMPA membrane (4.77 ± 0.67 vs. 1.34 ± 0.04) $\times 10^{-6}$ cm/s that may be explained by the metabolic activity of probiotic bacteria, i.e., the production of short-chain fatty acids, which lower the pH of the medium increases the amount of non-ionized molecular form of the drug. The total amount of gliclazide during incubation with bacteria, significantly decreased that could be a consequence of partial metabolism of the drug by enzymes of probiotic bacteria. Probiotic bacteria, naturally present as part of gut microflora and in the form of supplements, increase the permeability of gliclazide that may affect its absorption and bioavailability. This assumption might be addressed in future studies.

Keywords: probiotics, PAMPA, gliclazide, drug permeability, drug transport